

КРАТКОЕ ИЗЛОЖЕНИЕ ФОНЕТИКИ И ЛЕКСИКОЛОГИИ ТЮРКСКИХ ЯЗЫКОВ.

Вусала Асадова

Азербайджанский государственный педагогический университет, преподаватель кафедры
современного азербайджанского языка, доктор философии

E-mail: vasadova1984@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0005-4403-1284

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14046967>

Abstract: The article examines the general grammatical structure of modern Turkish languages. In the study, the phonetic structure and lexical units of Turkish languages were compared, and common and different features of phonemes were compared. At the same time, vowel sounds of Turkish languages were analyzed on the basis of vocal and consonantism poles. In the introductory part, he noted the periods of historical development of Turkic languages, gave information about the Ural-Altai language family and listed their distinctive features from Indo-European languages. In addition, the names of the states where Turkish languages and dialects are spoken are mentioned. The article also includes the classification of vowels and a brief explanation of consonant sounds. The third direction of the discussion is the explanation of some common words included in the lexicon of Turkish languages.

Keywords: Turkic languages, common, phonetics, elaborated, lexicon, word

BRIEF SUMMARY OF PHONETICS AND LEXICOLOGY OF TURKIC LANGUAGES

Vusala Asadova

Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, Teacher of the modern Azerbaijani language
department, Ph.D

E-mail: vasadova1984@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0005-4403-1284

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается общая грамматическая структура современных турецких языков. В исследовании сравнивались фонетическая структура и лексические единицы турецких языков, а также сравнивались общие и различные черты фонем. При этом гласные звуки турецких языков анализировались на основе полюсов вокализма и консонантизма. Во вступительной части он отметил периоды исторического развития тюркских языков, дал сведения об урало-алтайской языковой семье и перечислил их отличительные черты от индоевропейских языков. Кроме того, упоминаются названия государств, где говорят на турецких языках и диалектах. В статье также дана классификация гласных и краткое объяснение согласных звуков. Третье направление обсуждения - объяснение некоторых общих слов, входящих в лексикон турецких языков.

Ключевые слова: тюркские языки, общий, фонетика, разработанный, лексикон, слово

INTRODUCTION

If we consider the stages of the historical development of Turkic languages, we can divide those periods into: the oldest, ancient, middle and new Turkic periods.

- Altai and Hun periods (up to the 5th century AD)
- Ancient Turkic period (beginning of the 5th-10th centuries)

- Middle Turkic period (X-XV centuries)
- New and most recent Turkish periods (XVI-XX centuries).

According to some scientists, the Turkic languages included in the Ural-Altai languages, and according to the other part of them, belong to the family of languages, it has not been clearly studied until now. Thus, the disagreement of linguists and the different grammatical structure belonging to the Turkish languages make it possible for them to consider the group of Turkic languages as an independent language family. When we say Turkish language, Turkey is not meant as Turkish, it is understood as a language that includes all dialects. In the modern era, this language family is the native language of 180 million people. It is a language. These languages, which belong to the family of Turkic languages, which consists of 41 languages, dialects or dialects, are present in Azerbaijan, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Bashkirstan, Tatarstan, Tiwa, Chuvashia, Yakutia (Sakha), Nagorno-Altai and Khakassia. are genologically (originally) and typologically related languages of the local population, as well as a number of peoples of Iran, Iraq, Afghanistan, China, Bulgaria, Romania, former Yugoslavia and Albania. Also, Turkic languages are partially spoken in Dagestan (Kumugs, Nogais), Kabarda-Balkaria, Karachay-Circassian (Balkars, Karachays, Nogais), Stavropol (Nogais, Trukhmens), Moldova (Gagauzs), Lithuania (Karaims, Tatars), Ukraine (Crimean Tatars) and etc. also spread in places.

The history of the oldest Turkic period, which is the first period of this periodization, dates back to B.C. IV millennium BC V centuries are taken.

The characteristic distinguishing features of the period are evident in the Altai phase of the oldest Turkic period. One of the characteristic features of the Altai stage, which covers the IV-II millennia BC, is related to the lexical parallels manifested in the lexical composition. In 1938, the Estonian scientist F. Wiedemann studied the general features of the Ural-Altai language family and collected the features of this language family different from the Indo-European languages in the 14 articles below.

1. The most important feature of the Ural-Altai languages is phoneme harmony.
2. The words of these languages do not have any grammatical gender, i.e. they are not divided into masculine, feminine and imperfect: like modir (male) - midira (female), he (male) - she (female).
3. There are no articles (articles) such as Arabic "el-" and English "the" written at the beginning of the word with the word determining function.
4. All languages in the Ural-Altai language family are agglutinative languages. While acquisition and inflection are done with affixes, there is no change in the roots.
5. Possessive suffixes are used to denote nouns.
6. The forms of the verb are rich.
7. Indo-European languages use a postposition instead of a preposition.
8. Adjectives come before nouns: like a nice guy.
9. After number words, plural suffixes are not used. In Turkish, there are exceptions such as forty thieves and seven dwarfs.
10. Compared with the ablative suffix: Ayşe'den çalışın.
11. I- is used as an auxiliary verb. As if he was a hard worker.
12. Most of the Ural-Altai languages have a separate verb for negative action.
13. There is a question attachment.
14. Verb forms are used instead of conjunctions.

From these features, it is understood that phoneme harmony, which is a feature that distinguishes the Turkish language from world languages, is valid not only for the Turkish language, but also for other languages included in the language family to which Turkish belongs.

Relevance of the topic. The study of the grammatical structure of the modern Turkish language, the phonetic and morphological analysis, and the systematic study of the lexical units constitute the relevance of the topic in modern linguistics. The scientific instrumentation of the work with the main direction being directed to the classification of phonemes determines the relevance of the topic.

Objectives and tasks of the topic. Comparative study of Turkish languages is the main goal and tasks of the work:

- a) to give a general explanation of the phonetic structure of the modern Turkish language,
- b) take a brief look at the lexical structure of modern Turkish languages,

METHOD

The research was conducted on the basis of the historical-comparative method. The grammatical, phonetic, lexical structure of Turkic languages was examined and phonemes, lexical units, morphological particles were compared and analyzed by comparison method.

DISCUSSION

If we talk about the grammar of Turkic languages, we can note that all of this group of languages, with the exception of Chuvash and Yakut languages, can easily understand each other. In other words, when talking about the lexical, phonetic and grammatical structure of Turkic languages, it is based only on the monuments after the 6th century of the new era, and the ancient structure of Turkic languages is speculated about. At the same time, when making a generalization about the structure of Turkish languages, collecting information about the phonetic, lexical, morphological and syntactic structure of Turkish languages and conducting analysis in this direction creates a general picture of the grammatical structure of this language family. First of all, we can emphasize that all the phonetic regularities of modern Turkish languages have a historical character, that they have an unchanging phonetic structure, and that the phonetic structure is very similar in most Turkic languages. *"Two poles - vocalism and consonantism - are clearly distinguished in the phonetic structure of Turkish languages. These languages differ from other systematic languages precisely on the background of the colorful features of these two systems. It is characterized as a special language group.* (Kazimov, p. 32) Turkish languages have a vowel phoneme in common in terms of vocalism. *"The development of Turkish vocalism was determined by the divergence of u (o,u) and (ö,ü) sounds in ancient Ural-Altai languages".* Based on this feature, in order to determine the reason for the emergence of the vocalism of modern Turkish languages, it is first necessary to pay attention to the phonological features of vowel sounds, which are classified according to several principles. Let's list some of them:

- "1. According to the horizontal position of the tongue - in its lower, middle and upper positions. In this case, the main measure is the degree of elevation of the tongue.*
- 2. Front row, middle row and back row vowels are formed according to the horizontal position of the tongue;*
- 3. Depending on the position of the lips, lipped and non-lipped vowels are formed;*
- 4. Long and short vowels are distinguished according to the sign of the continuity of pronunciation (the difference in time between long and short vowels is approximately 2: 1 ratio)."* (Kazimov, p. 62)

The general transcription of the vowel sounds belonging to the Turkic languages was arranged by the linguist B.A. Serebrennikov and N.Z. Hajiyeva as follows:\

"a:- long a sound

a °- lipped a sound

e: - long e

ë- vowel between i and u

i:- long i sound short i sound

o:- long o sound ö- unlipitized o sound in Uzbek

ö:- long ö sound u:- long u sound

ü:- long ü sound ə- open e sound (a in the English word man)

ə: -long ə sound

ı:- long i sound

ь- weak i sound

Weak vowel between ь-ı and o" (B.A. Serebrennikov N.Z. Hajiyeva.S.12)

If we look at the general picture of common vowel sounds of Turkic languages, we can note that while Turkic languages with the vowel "ə" have 9 vowels, we can emphasize that Uzbek, which does not have the phonemes "a, ı and u", has six vowel sounds. In general, let's try to characterize the development of vocal phonemes in modern Turkish languages based on vowels:

The phoneme "a" has been fixed as an independent phoneme in all Turkic languages as an unlipitized, open, back palatal vowel. At the same time, the phoneme "a" does not undergo any changes when it is used with consonants and when it is part of a syllable. However, variants of the phoneme "a" are found in some Turkic languages, of which the lip phoneme "a^o" is used in Uzbek. While the orthographic sign of this phoneme is marked as o, its phonetic sound is like "a". For example, gora-kara, grass-horse, mol-mal, ax-axe, etc. While such a distinction is found in the use of a phoneme similar to the lipped phoneme "a" in the Tatar and Bashkir languages, the semi-lengthened version of the phoneme a is also observed in the Tuva language. *"In some Turkic languages, the vowel "a" is lengthened and sometimes even has a phonetic meaning" (Kazimov p. 64). For example: al-aal-kend, ay-aay-attitude (Tuva), khas-gaz, khaas-kemar, khara-kara, khaara-gece, as-bread, aas-mouth (khakas), par-get, paar- lung (shor), kar-gar, kaar-heat, yan-yaan-bgyuk (Altai), bas-bas, baash-yara (yakut), etc." (Verdiyev, p. 34). Dilçi alim İ.Kazimov qədim tiirk dillərində 8 sait səsin özlərinə maxsus refleksləri olduğunu " a-i reflex: gold-gold-iltan: honey-pil etc.*

a-a reflex: skin-akin, sdkiz-sakiz-sakkar, kel-kil-gsl, etc.

i-a reflex: kirak-kharpa (guv.)- kharpik (tuv.j. i-a reflex: sinnarnak- sanamak, sirt-sart, etc.

o-a reflex: neck-neck-mayin (puv.) etc.

Forming the ö-0 reflex as: kör-gor-kor//kur (cuv:) etc."(I.Kazimov, p. 34), he emphasized that phonetic processes should not have a historical character and be remembered by sound changes. He also noted that the changes in the vocal system of the ancient Tiirk language gradually took place differently in modern languages.

The phoneme "a", which is an unlipitized front palatal vowel, is used as a free vowel in Azerbaijani, Turkmen, Tatar, Bashkir, Uyghur and Kazakh languages and is also found in several dialects and dialects of Turkic languages. For example, Altai, Tuva, Nogai, Kalpak, etc. we can show examples found in languages like We also witness the transition of this phoneme to e and i in the Uighur language. For example, bel+belim, come-come, etc.

We also find that the phoneme "a" is preserved as a short vowel sound at the beginning of the word in Azerbaijani, New Uighur and Tofa languages. We can also find the transformation of this vowel sound into other vowels, of which the [a] sound is either drawn back and becomes [ɑ] sound, or as a result of its closure, it expresses the semi-open [ɐ] sound. As a result, the resulting [e] sound becomes narrower and sounds like [i] sound in some Turkic languages.

If we reflect on the history of Turkish consonantism, we can note that in Turkish languages, consonants with more or less complex articulation have often been simplified or turned into a sound of a completely different quality. *"The disappearance of bilateral l' and external z' consonants can be a clear example of this. In a number of Turkic languages, the difficult-to-articulate velar consonant κ has been transformed into the usual dental consonant κ or χ. This tendency can explain the weakening of cohesion in the pronunciation of affricates in most Turkic languages. This weakening ensured their simplification, and at the same time, for the Chuvash language and especially for the Siberian Turkic languages, consonants in the intervocalic position became ringing, caused a lot of assimilation of consonants, especially in affixes, and made it possible for k>ch and t>ch to pass in front of front-line vowels etc. G' \ ə. Weak sounds of the ğ' type appeared unstable in intervocalic position or in front of a plosive consonant. The transformation of the prepositional sound y into an affricate c observed in most Turkic languages can also be explained by internal factors. The initial sounds of the word carry more information. Therefore, in every language, there is a tendency to ensure that the beginning of the word is heard better. In this case, the jingling affricate has a great advantage over the consonant y, which has a weak articulation. Of course, in individual cases, the change of voices can be determined by external reasons. The radical change of consonantism in the Yakut language, the emergence of breathy plosive consonants in some Turkic languages of the Caucasus, Siberia, and China, the complete transformation of the / and /' sounds into the Middle European / sound in the Uzbek language, etc. It is difficult to explain without taking into account the influencing possibilities of the substrate language."* (B.A. Serebrennikov, N.Z. Hajiyeva.S.p.96)

In addition, if we look at the shared meanings of the lexical composition belonging to this language family, we can see that each word has a different meaning in different dialects. For example.

Although the Kazakh and Uzbek languages are different, many common features are observed:

– Suffix +lĭK forming an adjective from geographical names, e.g. Gas. We stopped in Kazakhstan

'Kazakhstan' and Uzb. Uzbekistliq 'from Uzbekistan';

- Participant expressing necessity, Kaz. -AtIn, e.g. don't be a fool

Uzb. -dAğAn, e.g. no room for help 'no one will help'
no';

- The sentence formed with the verbs "to think, to think" is of the same type
is done, e.g. gas. dep silent, Uzb. deb o'ylaysit 'you think';

– traditional event, Kaz. usual, Uzb. express with phrase day
is done, see. gas. ädettegiden kobirek, Ozb. more than time
more than ever';

- Explore previous events. and Uzb. +dAn is represented by a nasal/nasal, e.g.
gas. osidan eki apta burin, Uzb. two weeks later nose 'Two weeks later
before';

– Kaz means 'to understand', with multiple subjects and objects. eighty- [Otkuz], Uzb. o'tkaz- is met with actions, e.g. election pass-/saylav ötkiz- 'to choose';

- market duration Far. Expressed by the word narh, e.g. gas. naryk, Uzb. Price free market/free price 'free market', cf.

Osm. price 'fiat'

Some words specific to the Turkic languages of Central Asia define the boundaries of the region. Aşıp is also used in other parts of the Turkic world, e.g. Gas. If we apply

Dirt. bōrsok, Alt. bürzak ~ badger,

Right. pōrsok 'fried food made from dough, fried in oil'; Kaz., Uzb., Application. botga, Cyrus. botko, Alt. botko ~ motko ~ motka, Hak. pothi 'palam'.

It is quite durable. Nevertheless, language interaction is new in the region in question. That is why the Ancient Turkic lexicon can be conditionally systematized into 3 groups:

1) nouns; abag-ayag, bor-cakhyr, sub-su, oq-ana, ulus-elka, tana-karsi, yir-yer, tōn-dōn, bolun-asr, ocuk-oaq, ic-ish, etc.

2) words denoting signs and qualities; clear-kinli, white-white, echi-big, yaguk-near, bulga-blurry, salt-salt, etc.

3) words denoting action; ölut- to kill, gray-poz, start, sink; overturn, collapse, collapse, etc.

Taking into account the existence of words that belong to the original Turkic languages belonging to each of the groups, as well as the words acquired over time, we can note that the lexical units of the languages belonging to the Turkic language family are a set of words that contain a comprehensive and complex meaning.

THE RESULT

We can summarize what has been said in general in several directions:

1. The classification of vowel and consonant sounds follows the same distribution in all Turkish languages, and the variant of some sounds shows itself, while some vowel sounds are not processed in some variants of Turkish languages and it was found that they have variants.

2. When reviewing some of the lexical units, meaning variants were found. You showed yourself the expression in each dialect with a separate word.

Literature

1. B. A. Serebrennikov N. Z. Hajiyeva. Comparative historical grammar of Turkic languages, Baku, 2020, P.377
2. I. Kazimov. Comparative phonetics of modern Turkish languages. Volume I. Science and education, 2011, p. 193
3. Kazimov I. Turkish languages comparative morphology, volume III. Baku, Elm, 2019. 304 p.
4. Maharramli B. Historical lexicology of Turkish languages. Baku, 2017, 270 pages